

Impact of Successor's Personality Traits on Small & Medium Enterprise (SME) Family Business Succession

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Abstract- *This study analyses the personality traits of the successor by implementing the big five-personality trait theory on the small and medium enterprise family businesses. The purpose of this study is to enhance the life duration of small and medium family business. The results of this study reveal that the attention of incumbent/founder towards the personality traits of successor is as vital as the continuity of the business. The three personality traits Openness, Extroversion and consciousness are more important for the successful continuity of the small and medium enterprise family business however, agreeableness personality traits should try to keep under control and neuroticism has no impact over the succession planning of family business. Family businesses are backbone for the economy of any country so a deep eye must be on family businesses with respect to economy.*

Keywords: *Personality Traits, Small and Medium Enterprise, Family Business Succession*

I. INTRODUCTION

A business involving two or more than two members of family and sustaining the control or ownership within the family called a family business. Business owned by family might be the sustaining from generations. Family businesses operated by the members of families are not mere businesses but potential contributors towards the economy of any country and its contributions never be denied. In the era of modernism and new trends family businesses are dynamic and important contributors in the world's economy. Family businesses play a vital role for generating employments and revenues while contribute in the GDP of developed and developing countries (Jinchuan & Weiwei, 2017). The businesses, which are family based, have huge share, which starts from 80% and goes to 98% amongst all the businesses in the world market of business. It also gives opportunity of employment to people consisting 50% to 75% share in total population of the world (Setiono, 2016). Organizations related to family businesses claims that "Family business represents 80% of the worldwide companies and forming the economy."

It was found in the study that the countries which are not developed and those countries which have good economies both built themselves again to make sure the survival and strength because of businesses owned by families. The small family businesses are heavily been focused by latest studies. (Marler, Botero, & De Massis, 2017) state the reason that expectations are very high from family businesses to make market better, keeping economic growth high, providing opportunities of employment and work like a system in the economy and society. (Ibrahim, Dumas, & McGuire, 2015) state that Succession is that sort of problem, which is not common because it comes into existence because of the family businesses and it shifts the business from founder to next generation.

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Entrepreneurship definitely gives a person bundle of opportunities that allows him to stay independent, enjoy higher financial return and plays important role in economy development. Business operates like machine in social betterment, employment increasing and economic development. It also suggests that entrepreneurship and personality characteristics have positive relation to each other (Chaston, 2017). Entrepreneurs are those people who have unique and special qualities in their personalities. The traits like strong dedication for social vision, the activities to be consistent, creativity, making new friends and creating networks can generate handsome revenues. The objective of this study is to identify the impact of successor's a personality trait on the succession transition of small and medium enterprise business to subsequent generation.

It has been defined by (Ibrahim, Dumas, & McGuire, 2015) defines the family business in a way that family business is owned by the members of the family and they follow the same thought policies and strategy as learned by family and transferred to them. Most crucial issue in the family firms is succession. A proper succession process presents family businesses an opportunity to choose the competent and effective leaders that can revitalize their businesses. (Setiono, 2016) claims that inability to efficiently direct and arrange the transfer of business to the other generation in a proper channel are the main descriptions for the extreme collapsing frequency in first and 2nd generation of family-owned businesses. There are so many studies that explain the succession planning as important process planning. It is a fact that family businesses have lower survival rate, 1/3 businesses continue to exist for the 2nd generation & only 15% gets life for the 3rd generation.

Big five-personality trait theory implemented in this study to check either which personality trait of successor can contribute for the successful transition of business from one generation to subsequent generation. According to (Zillig, Hemenover, & Dienstbier, 2002) operationalize the five traits of personality in their study. The big five-personality trait theory consists of five variables, which are conscientiousness, extraversion, openness, agreeableness and neuroticism. We have operationalized these variables of personality trait theory below.

(Sharma, Chua, & Chrisman, 2000) said that neuroticism personality trait consists of two dimensions, which are volatility and withdrawal. The volatility dimension consist of 9 elements which are get upset easily, change mood, mood goes up and down easily, get agitated, stirred up easily, rarely get irritated, emotions under control, lose composure and easily annoyed. However, the second dimension of neuroticism is withdrawal. (Chlosta, Patzelt, Klein, & Dormann, 2012) stated that there are two dimensions of extraversion, which are enthusiasm and assertiveness. The enthusiasm dimension consists of nine elements which are; making friends, warm up quickly to others, show happiness feelings, having fun, laugh, hard to get to know, keep others at distance, caught up in excitement and enthusiastic person.

According to (Beverland, 2013) openness are aesthetic sense, believe in importance of art, love to reflect things, deeply immersed in music, see beauty in things, need for creative outlet, like poetry, seldom get lost in thoughts, seldom daydream, seldom notice to emotional aspects of painting and picture. (Gomba & Kele, 2016) there are two dimensions of agreeableness, which are compassion and politeness. The compassion dimension consist of 10 elements which are; other's emotions feeling, other's well-being inquiry, sympathize with other's feeling, interest in other's lives, like to do things for others, interest in other's problems, bothered with other's need, having feelings for others, take time for others, have soft side for others.

According to (Rauch & Frese, 2007) there are two dimension of conscientiousness, which is industriousness and orderliness. The industriousness dimension consists of 9 elements which are; finish the started work, get things done quickly, time wastage, feel difficult to work, mess things, putting mind on task, postpone decision and distracted. While second important dimension of conscientiousness is orderliness.

II. LITERATURE

A person with conscientiousness characteristics have main focus in process of individual level of accomplishment, association and scheduling, and person who have ability to control himself and as well as have strength to accept the norms and values, last but not least show responsibility toward others. Some main traits of conscientiousness are, they are hardworking and motivated to their goals and face every type of problems in which they achieve their goals and these are quite related with entrepreneurship. Other component of conscientiousness characteristic another way of work entity and determination quite related with the

entrepreneurial character (Yordanova, 2017) said that determination is called for by entrepreneurial work, whereas others have main focus on motivation, willpower, and hard work. Entrepreneurship based on the organization that entities attracted to roles that match their personality and their advantages especially conscientious people, and no doubt, these people accept to relate with entrepreneurial firm act. Hesitantly many intellectuals perceive that conscientiousness is the main motivational variable. Major dependable personality interpreter of job performance diagonally all types of work and field (Khajeheian, 2017) the firms which were concerned with entrepreneurship were closely observed and it was concluded that motivation ability in an entrepreneur was behind the progress of the firm.

Openness is practical which is pretty opposite from spiritual ability but it's connected with intelligence, such as conflicting thoughts (Woodfield et al., 2017) the key feature of entrepreneurship is originality and tendency, which used to bring out innovative change or, in Schumpeter's (1942/1976) famous phrase, "creative destruction." In every range of entrepreneurs who are seen to be successful have ability to make a plan and vision whereas narrow minded thinkers don't do such things. Motivation, welcoming a chance of success is concerned with vision and openness thinking of an entrepreneur. Up to some limit entrepreneurs depend on being original or what they are for solving regular issues, moreover for making policies having less resources (Ramadani, Hisrich, Anggadwita, & Alamanda, 2017) it is not about work performance all the time openness is linked with performing in training areas and academies or such learning place.

People who have higher ratio on extraversion use to connect in the society, like to meet people in friendly manners and they tend to win situations and events in the society. They keep themselves inspire and motivated having positive thoughts and feelings. Such people are more energetic, active and not afraid to be straight forward. Qualities like being positive, staying excited and having more active living ability are attached with the people considered to be entrepreneurs (O'Leary, Swaffin-Smith, & Fakoussa, 2017) study of Holland's classification shows that the people who are related with business and adopting it as their occupation are extraverts. The career as an entrepreneur seems to be more attractive and inspiring rather than other occupations that are why it is more favourite by extraverts.

Moreover, entrepreneurs lead the groups of their working people and the traits of extravert people like being social, friendly, and active all attached with people who considered extravert (Nelson & Constantinidis, 2017) the quality of extraversion and attaching with leading a business forces us to think that extraverts could be more attracted towards business and entrepreneurship. It can link that entrepreneur's ratio of being extravert linked to their performance positively. There are so many tasks in which entrepreneurs are busy and doing it routine wise like going very much social having connections with people and making a big network and also keeping good relations with partners, customers and people who supply products to them.

Agreeableness is element in which we evaluate the one's behaviour and action towards other. The main properties of high agreeableness described as person who is quite polite in nature responsible and cooperative. The most important quality of agreeableness personality is that they are quite different from others and face opposition in any condition and no doubt, they show compassion and solve the problems with positive intention.

According to (Adedayo, Olanipekun, & Ojo, 2016) people on high level of agreeableness are pretty social like: social work and teaching rather than firms, because those professionals are quite attractive and no doubt in that case they can interact with others and easily understand other person needs. Entrepreneurship requires retreating and shunning employment arrangements which are out dated and these can improve the level of self-confidence and make relations good. It made compulsory by entrepreneurship to make profitable firm according to the interests and needs of entrepreneur (Cater & Young, 2016). Some important qualities for becoming successful are running through tough negotiations, finding out interest of business and knowing to tackle others in the stream (Bizri, 2016). Stable on such judgment, study anticipated that good entrepreneurs are not much agreeable. In this research, study will check the big five-personality traits, to assess successor's personality and practice such processes to forecast the possibility of long-term survival of family business.

It has been said by (Merchant, Kumar, & Mallik, 2017) neuroticism personality trait consists of two dimensions, which are volatility and withdrawal. The volatility dimension consist of 9 elements which are get upset easily, change mood, mood goes up and down easily, get agitated, stirred up easily, rarely get irritated,

emotions under control, lose composure and easily annoyed. However, the second dimension of neuroticism is withdrawal. This study (Marler et al., 2017) takes into account different dimensions of personality to have an effect on students' career accommodation, optimism, and cognition. Students with higher valuation on openness proved to have better career decisiveness, but a noteworthy pessimistic impact of neuroticism. Though, the significant communication of neuroticism and awareness about career decisiveness suggests that students who face worries and struggle they have not much know how about career, consequently, there will be more complexities in their career decision-making.

Successors are the vital part of family business. Therefore, Successor having capabilities and qualities may lead business towards new dimensions. Personality traits of the successor (Cater & Young, 2016) were rated as the most important in the organizational studies. Most family business owners wish the next generation would take over their firms while being a striking contrast, only 16% of their kids would like to, making up only 1/3 of the samples with a clear intention. As per (Nuthall & Old, 2017) discovers that the offspring's succession situation in reality does not coincide with their intentions. Only 24.24% are willing to enter the enterprise after the graduation, while in reality it is 60.61%.

(Bizri, 2016) comment that maintaining continuity of a family-owned business is perhaps one of the toughest management jobs on the globe, because, over and above the normal typical business challenges, family businesses also face challenges of handling the human emotions associated with family power struggles, sibling rivalry, upholding family values, family conflict, parents oppressive customs, favouritism, stagnation, succession and rigidity. (Neubauer & Lank, 2016) parent's plans about the matters of succession and children's interest in getting ready for succession by their parents prove crucial. The parents who prepare their children through knowledge and practice for family business tend to play in important role in their offspring's succession plan.

Figure No 1 Theoretical Framework

H1: There is significant relationship between extraversion and small and medium family business succession planning.

H2: There is significant relation between agreeableness personality trait and small and medium family business succession planning.

H3: There is significant relation between conscientiousness traits of successor with small and medium family business succession planning.

H4: There is significant relation between neuroticism trait of successor and small and medium family business succession.

H5: There exist significant relationship between openness traits and small and medium family business succession planning.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Model Equation:

$$\text{Family Business Succession} = f (B_0+B_1X_1+B_2X_2+B_3X_3+B_4X_4+B_5X_5)$$

Where:

- X1= Extraversion
- X2= Agreeableness
- X3= Conscientiousness
- X4= Neuroticism
- X5= Openness

The population that’s targeted in this research is small family business run by more than one family members. Study population is founder who established the business and now business is running under surveillance of founder and second generation, third generation or fourth generation. This study conducted in the context of Punjab Pakistan and the sample in this study is small and medium family business running under the surveillance of founder and second-generation successor, third generation successor or fourth generation successor in Lahore and Faisalabad district. Family business had chosen in which at least two members of same family are working with other’s coordination. The criteria which distinguished the family owned business to a sole proprietor business are years of establishment, firm’s generation handling business and age of business. Data collected from almost all members of family, which were involved in that business so far. This empirical study involves population of 84 small family businesses in Punjab Pakistan.

In this study, non-probability, purposive sampling technique is used. Heterogeneous sampling is a purposive sampling technique, which is use to estimate broad range of perspective relating to study; that is maximum variation sampling as well. Sample size of the study is calculated by using the formula below.

$ss = Z^2 * (\text{Shepherd \& Zacharakis}) * (1-p) / c^2$, Where: Z=Z value (e.g. 1.96 For 95% confidence level), p = percentage picking a choice, expressed as decimal (.5 used for sample size needed).

c = confidence interval, expressed as decimal Five Likert scales used in questionnaire from:

- 1- Never
- 2 – Rarely
- 3 – Sometimes
- 4 – Often
- 5 – Always

Note. The scales are described in the following article: DeYoung, C. G., Quilty, L. C., & Peterson, J. B. (2007). Between facets and domains: 10 aspects of the Big Five. Journal of Personality and Social Psychology. 93, 880-896.

Reliability:

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>items</i>
Extraversion	0.693	0.748	14
Agreeableness	0.672	0.711	11
Conscientiousness	0.570	.642	15
Neuroticism	0.723	0.742	16
Openness	0.726	0.813	13
SME Family Business Succession	0.758	0.813	07

Table: I

IV. RESULTS

The research methodology adopted in this study requires data collection from small family business running under the surveillance of founder and second-generation successor, third generation successor or fourth generation successor. Family business had chosen in which at least two members of same family are working with other’s coordination. The criteria which distinguished the family owned business to a sole proprietor business are years of establishment, firm’s generation handling business and age of business. Data collected from almost all members of family, which were involved in that business so far.

		M.C.O	M.E.A	M.O.Q	M.A.Q	M.N.Q	M.F.B
N		294	294	294	294	294	294
	Mean	3.24	3.47	3.43	3.08	2.47	2.98
Normal Parameters	Std. Deviation	.716	1.054	.607	.341	.500	.822
	Absolute	.266	.326	.316	.493	.357	.230
	Positive	.266	.325	.270	.493	.357	.230
	Negative	-.223	-.328	-.316	-.385	-.325	-.219
Kolmogorov Smirnov		4.568	5.624	5.427	8.446	6.117	3.949
	Sig.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

Table: II

In the above table, N value shows, data collected from 294 respondents who are running family business. Maximum mean value is 3.24 while minimum mean value is 2.47, which reveal that response given by the respondents in near the mean and there exist no much difference in the mean between the independent variable. Standard deviation also shows that data is less deviated from the mean. Above table shows three most extreme differences which absolute, positive and negative. These extreme mean values are within Z distribution, which is between +1.96 to -1.96, which shows data collected in this study is normally distributed.

Bi-Variate Correlation:

Correlation	Consciousness	Extroversion	Openness	Agreeableness	Neuroticism	Family Business Succession
Consciousness	1					
Extroversion	.621	1				
Openness	.037	.277	1			
Agreeableness	-.170	-.314	.176	1		
Neuroticism	.409	.696	.618	-.003	1	
Succession	.502	.810	.325	-.327	.621	1

Table: III

The above table shows the relationship between consciousness, extroversion, openness, agreeableness, neuroticism and succession. The value of correlation between consciousness and extroversion is 0.621 which shows there is strong positive correlation between consciousness and extroversion. The value of correlation between consciousness and openness is .037, which shows there is positive slight almost negligible relationship between consciousness and openness. The correlation between consciousness and agreeableness in -.170, which shows there is negative slight almost negligible correlation. Therefore, successor possessing high consciousness personality trait, possess less agreeableness. The value of correlation between consciousness and neuroticism is 0.409, which means successor having consciousness personality trait have moderate level of neuroticism.

The value of correlation between consciousness and family business succession is 0.502, which shows consciousness personality trait has moderately and positively affects the family business succession. The value of relationship between extroversion and openness is 0.277, which shows there is positive Small but definite relationship between extroversion and openness. The successor having extroversion personality trait must have 27.7% openness quality. However the correlation between extroversion and agreeableness is -.314, which shows there is negative small but definite relationship. Moreover, the value of correlation between extroversion and neuroticism is 0.696, which shows there is positive moderate relationship. In addition, the value of correlation between extroversion and succession is 0.810, which shows there is high positive relationship between these two variables.

It shows that successor having extroversion qualities is more affective for family business survival. The value of correlation between openness and agreeableness is 0.176, which shows there is positive slight but negligible relationship. However, the value of correlation between openness personality trait and neuroticism

personality trait is .618, which shows there is moderate level of relationship. Moreover, the value of relationship between openness and family business succession is .325 means openness personality trait has positive small but definite relationship with succession. The correlation value between agreeableness and neuroticism is -0.003, which shows there is negative small but negligible relationship on the other hand agreeableness, has negative small but definite relationship with family business succession. So results shows that, successor having agreeableness personality trait negatively affect the succession of family business. The value of correlation between neuroticism and succession is .621, which shows there is moderate positive relationship between neuroticism and succession. Thus, results shows neuroticism personality trait plays its vital role for the survival of family business up to next generation.

Multiple Regression Model:

Independent variable	Beta	t-value	Sig.
(Nelson & Constantinidis)	-1.327	-.202	0.840
Consciousness	.550	-0.001	0.451
Extroversion	.634	0.755	0.000
Openness	.552	11.397	0.008
Agreeableness	.521	-3.587	.000
Neuroticism	.794	1.153	0.250
R	.826		
R ²	.682		
Adjusted R ²	.676		
F	126.053		

Table: IV

The table above is multiple regressions implemented in this study. This table explains the relationship between independent variables, which are consciousness, Extraversion, Neuroticism, agreeableness, and openness and dependant variable is family business succession. This table explains up to what extent big-five personality theory effects on the succession process so that family business can be transfer to next generation. The table named coefficient table shows the effect and strength of independent variables, which are consciousness, Extraversion, Neuroticism, agreeableness and openness on dependant variable, which is family business succession. This table helps to determine the rejection or acceptance of proposed hypothesis of this study. Before interpretation of regression co efficient first checks the overall F-statistics and assumption of linear regression. Under the UN standardized coefficient column “B” is listed. In the unit of Z score there are standardize coefficient carrying the same information. In the next column, there is t- statistics and furtherance there is P- value.

Estimated Model Coefficient/Multiple linear regression model:

The structural equation predicts the exact effect of independent variables, which are consciousness, Extraversion, Neuroticism, agreeableness, and openness over dependant variable family business succession. Predicted Succession planning = 1.327 + (0.794 X Neuroticism) + (0.521 X Agreeableness) + (0.552 X Openness) + (0.634 X Extraversion) + (0.550 X Consciousness) Co-efficient UN standardize shows how much effect of independent variables on dependant variable when all other dependent variables are constant. The standardize coefficient reveals that one unit increase in neuroticism personality trait of family business successor there will be positive effect on succession process of family business. One unit increase in agreeableness personality trait of family business successor there is negative effect on succession process of family business. One unit increase in openness personality trait of family business successor there is strong positive effect on succession process of family business. One unit increase in extraversion personality trait of family business successor there is positive effect on succession process of family business. One unit increase in

consciousness personality trait of family business successor there is positive effect on succession process of family business. Thus, grooming in personality trait of successor, which are openness, extraversion and consciousness may help to sustain family business up to subsequent generations.

Statistical Framework:

Neuroticism (N) $b=0.069$, $t(298) = 1.153$ and $P = 0.250$. One of important element of Big-Five personality trait theory, Neuroticism shows that one unit increase in neuroticism there is .069 impacts on succession process. The t value of Neuroticism is 1.153, which is less than two, which shows that there exist no relationship between neuroticism and succession process of family business. The sig value named P value is 0.250, which is more than .05, thus we can accept (H_04): Neuroticism has no positive association with family business succession planning. Therefore, it is assume that Neuroticism personality trait of a successor does not contribute in the succession process of family business and enhancement in life duration of family business. A successor having only one Neuroticism personality trait cannot help family business to shift in subsequent generation successfully.

Agreeableness (A) $b= -0.132$, $t(298) = -3.587$ and $P = 0.000$. Agreeableness is vital element of Big-Five personality trait theory as well. The results obtained by implementing multiple regression models shows that one unit increase in agreeableness personality trait of successor there exist negative strong effect on succession process of family business. The t value of agreeableness is -3.587 so it is above two and sig/P value is 0.000, which is less than alpha 0.05. Thus, we can reject (H_02): Agreeableness has no positive significant impact on family business succession planning. Therefore it is assumed that agreeableness personality trait of a successor does contribute in the succession process. A successor having strong agreeableness personality trait does not provide benefits for the success of succession planning of family business. Results show that successor should not have strong agreeableness traits. Therefore, successor must have strong decision-making and determinant quality for success and life enhancement of family business. Openness (O) $b=0.120$, $t(298) = 2.690$ and $P = 0.008$.

Openness is another element of Big-Five personality trait theory. Multiple regression models shows that one unit increase in openness personality trait of successor there exist positive strong effect on succession process of family business. The t value of openness personality trait is 2.690 which is greater than 2 so this indicate that openness has positive significant impact while sig value is 0.008 which is less than .05 which also shows that openness personality trait of successor contributes for the successful transition of family business from one generation to subsequent generation. Therefore, we reject (H_05): There exist no relationship between openness and family business succession planning. These results also show that successor having openness

personality trait possesses imaginative, curious and open minded qualities which contribute for handling family business successfully in addition, take steps for long term survival of family business. Extraversion (E) $b=.667$, $t(298)=11.397$ and $P=0.000$. Extraversion is another important element upon which Big-Five personality trait theory consist.

Multiple regression models implemented in this study shows that one unit increase in extraversion personality trait of successor there exist positive strong effect on succession process of family business. The t value of extraversion is 11.397 so it is above two and sig/P value is 0.000, which is less than alpha 0.05. Thus, we can reject (H_0): Extraversion has no positive significant effect on family business succession planning. Therefore, it assumed that extraversion personality trait of a successor does contribute in the succession process of family business. A successor having strong extraversion personality trait does provide benefits for the success of succession planning of family business.

Results show that successor who is more social, talkative, energetic and assertive influence more on succession process and play its role for transition of family business from one generation to subsequent generation. Conscience (C) $b=0.032$, $t(298)=.755$ and $P=0.451$. Conscience is another element of Big-Five personality trait theory. Multiple regression models shows that one unit increase in Conscience personality trait of successor there exist positive strong effect on succession process of family business. The t value of Conscience personality trait is .775 which is less than 2 so this indicate that Conscience has positive significant impact while sig value is 0.000 which is more than .05 which also shows that Conscience personality trait of successor contribute for the successful transition of family business from one generation to subsequent generation. Therefore, we accept, (H_0): Conscience has no positive relationship with family business succession planning. These results also show that successor having Conscience personality trait is more organized, disciplined, and is very careful in certain situations which contribute for handling family business successfully in addition, take steps to keep align tasks and responsibilities.

The value of 'R' shows the relationship between the independent variables and dependant variable. The value of R is .826, which shows there is very strong relationship between the conscience, Extraversion, Neuroticism, agreeableness, and openness and family business succession. Next row is R square, which called co-efficient of determination as well. It shows the statistical fitness of model. R square is percentage of variance and value of R square is 68.2%, which is good percentage. R square is less preferable than adjusted R square as adjusted R square estimates number of coefficient and sample size estimated. Normally R square value is larger than Adjusted R square.

The value of adjusted R square in the above table shows that by increasing conscience, Extraversion, Neuroticism, agreeableness, and openness 67.6% succession process in family business can be successful. So it can interpreted, Big-Five personality trait theory is implementable on successor of family business likewise on entrepreneur. The F value, which is 126.053, determines that there is significant effect of our independent variables, which are conscience, Extraversion, Neuroticism, agreeableness and openness over dependent variable institutional learning. The sig value also named P value is .000, which is less than alpha .05. Thus, it is conclude that the result of analysis of variance is significant.

V. CONCLUSION

The present study carried out to enhance the life duration of family business in Pakistan As literature shows the intensive trend of shutting down the family business. As (Ward, 2011) reveals that only 30% business survive till 2nd generation; 13 % up to 3rd generation while 3% business left which transfer in fourth generation. Moreover, these businesses are more important for any country as they contribute towards the economy. The most of founder putt off the succession planning, as they are not aware of the importance of succession planning. Succession planning in family business contains great risks and opportunities. The great magnitude of risk for those prevailing business: that do not bother for the safe transaction of business from one generation to subsequent capable and interested generation. The opportunity for those who pay attention well in time for developing and training the potential successor and introduce him/her among the business stakeholder as business succession takes years to be accomplish. A proper succession plan can help ensure that your retirement needs met and that the business you worked so hard to build will continue to flourish for years. The results of

this study show that it is quite requisite that personality traits of the successor must match with the family business. Deviation of interest of successor from the family business may results in depilation of the business.

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